

POLAND

POLAND

**GRAMMATICAL PROBLEMS TRANSLATING ENGLISH INTO
RUSSIAN.****Xushbokova Muxlisa**

Student of National University of Uzbekistan

Muxlisa.xushvaqova@icloud.com

+998979003638

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7440594>

Abstract: This paper is devoted to the research of an important question in translation studies, i.e. the study of syntactic problems of translation from English into Russian. The phenomenon draws much attention because of the reason that the theory of translation is not fully developed in the country, and all the linguistic works devoted to the problem of translation from any foreign language into the Russian language somehow contribute to the solution of the problem. More specifically, translation is the process and result of creating in a target, or, translating, language a text which has approximately the same communicative value as the corresponding text in the source language. A translator makes possible the exchange of information between the users of different languages by producing a text in the target language which has an identical communicative value with the source text. This target text is not fully similar to the source text as to its form or content due to the limitations imposed by the formal and semantic differences between the source language and the target language.

Key words: semantic, grammar, communicative, target, category It is well known that languages differ in their grammatical structure. Apart from having different grammatical categories they differ in the use of those categories that seem to be similar. This naturally results in the necessity to introduce some grammatical changes in the translated version of any text. These changes depend on the character of correlation between the grammatical norms of the source and target languages. Various as they are, all the possible changes may be classed under four main types: transpositions, replacements, additions, and omissions.

There may appear a necessity to rearrange elements of different levels: words, phrases, clauses or even sentences. Transposition of words and phrases may be caused by various reasons: differences in the accepted word order in the source language and the target language, presence or absence of emphasis, differences in the means of communicative syntax.

Each sentence can be spoken of in different aspects. A syntactic aspect implies the sentence analysis in terms of parts of the sentence (sentence subject, predicate, object, attribute, adverbial modifier). Syntax reveals the relation of

sentence parts to each other. A semantic aspect implies the relation of sentence components to the elements of the real situation named by the sentence. This can be done in terms of case grammar or reference theory, or by singling out the agent, object and other semantic roles. A third aspect is pragmatic, or communicative. It implies the relation of the sentence to its users. The speaker makes up a sentence so as to stress logically this or that part of the information conveyed by the sentence. Therefore, this type of sentence structure is called information (communicative) structure, and this type of sentence analysis is referred to as actual division of the sentence, or functional sentence perspective. Normally, each sentence develops from a known piece of information, called the theme, to a new one, called the rheme. The rhematic component is the information center of the sentence. It is logically stressed. It can be easily singled out in speech by contrasting it to some other word: The early bird catches the worm, not the trap. The early bird catches the worm, not the late one. The rhematic word usually answers a special question: e.g., Whom does the early bird catch? - The early bird catches the worm. What kind of bird catches the worm? - The early bird catches the worm.

In addition to the methods of contrasting and questioning, there are some other signals for the rhematic component. They include:

the indefinite article of the sentence subject: A little evil is often necessary for obtaining a great good. a long extended part of the sentence; compare: Many people saw it. - People saw it. negation: Not he who has much is rich, but he who gives much. intensifiers (only, even, just, such as, etc.): Only the educated are free. (Cf. The educated are free.) some special constructions (there is; it is... (who); passive constructions with the by-agent expressed): It is human nature to think wisely and to act foolishly.

The sentence communicative structure is different in English and in Russian. In Russian it is more rigid, which compensates a loose word order of the sentence. English fixed word order, on the other hand, is compensated by a free, to some extent, functional sentence perspective. In Russian neutral style, the theme precedes the rheme, which means that a logically stressed part of the sentence is in the final position. In English, the rheme can be interrupted by the theme or even precede the theme: There is an unknown word in the text. (T-R-T) - В тексте есть незнакомое слово. (T-R).

Word order change due to the functional sentence perspective When the English and Russian functional sentence perspectives do not coincide, a word order change is applied in translation.

Thus, the rhematic subject in English usually takes the initial position, whereas in Russian it should be placed at the end of the sentence: A faint perfume of jasmine came through the open window. (O.Wilde) - Сквозь открытое окно доносился легкий аромат жасмина. A waitress came to their table. - К их столику подошла официантка.

This transformation is evident in comparing the structures with the subjects introduced by the definite and indefinite articles. A sentence that has the definite article with the subject has the same word order: The woman entered the house. - Женщина вошла в дом. On the other hand, a word order change takes place in a similar sentence if its subject is determined by the indefinite article: A woman entered the house. - В дом вошла женщина.

To emphasize the rhematic subject of the sentence, the construction it is ... that (who) can be used in English. For example, It is not by means of any tricks or devices that the remarkable effect of Milton's verse is produced. - Удивительный эффект стихов Мильтона объясняется вовсе не какими-то особыми ухищрениями. The rhematic component is positioned at the end of the Russian sentence. Another example: It was the Russian-born American physicist Vladimir Zworykin who made the first electronic television in the 1920s. - Именно Владимир Зворыкин, американский физик русского происхождения, создал электронный телевизор в 20-х годах XX столетия. In Russian, the emphasis on the semantic center of the sentence is made either with the help of the intensifier (именно), or else the meaning can be rendered through a change of word order: Электронный телевизор в 20-х годах XX столетия создал Владимир Зворыкин, американский физик русского происхождения.

Thematic components in Russian are shifted to the initial position, which often happens with objects and adverbial modifiers: It was early for that. - Для этого еще было рано. A typical case is the sentence introduced by there is/are. Here the subject is rhematic and the adverbial modifier of place is thematic. Therefore, the construction is normally translated into Russian with the adverbial in the initial position: There is a book on the table. - На столе лежит книга. Compare this sentence with one of a thematic subject: The book is on the table. - Книга лежит на столе. If there is no adverbial modifier of place in the English sentence (to start the translation), the sentence beginning with there is is rendered in Russian by the verb существует: There are three kinds of solid body. - Существует три вида твердого тела.

Adverbial modifiers of place and time are usually mirrored in translation. Being thematic, they are positioned in the beginning of the Russian sentence, and in English they take the final position: Вчера в Москве состоялась встреча президента России с президентом Франции. - A meeting of the Russian president and the French president was held in Moscow yesterday.

A rhematic component expressing the agent of the action in the passive construction cannot be placed as the initial subject of the translated sentence: The telephone was invented by A. Bell. corresponds to Телефон изобрел А. Белл. (not to А. Белл изобрел телефон.)

To conclude: The difficulties that can of specific difficulty for a translator in the process of translation from English into Russian may be the absence of those grammar forms available in English. One of the most important syntactic peculiarities of the English language is the existence of secondary predication created by various participial and infinitive constructions. These constructions are included in the structure of simple sentences in English while Russian simple sentences have only one predicative center. This way leads to the necessity of substituting English composite sentences for simple sentences of the translation text. Actually, translation of specifically English grammatical constructions consists of two stages: first it is necessary to understand their meaning and then find a corresponding way of expressing it in Russian. For the purpose of translation, grammar does not exist separately. It is not the grammatical form but the grammatical meaning that is of primary concern for a translator or an interpreter. A mistake in grammar (whether it is a misunderstood construction of the source language or a wrong variant in the target language) always tells on the sense and logic of the text. As soon as the sense and logic of a sentence stop to be transparent it is necessary to stop and look for a mistake in the translation.

References:

1. Brinton E., Cruz E., Ortizy Ortiz, R. & White C. Translation Strategies. London: Macmillan, 1981.
2. Duff A. Translation, 1989. Oxford: Oxford University Press.
3. Barhudarov. Language and translation. Moscow, 1975.
4. Levitskaya T.R and Fiterman A.M. Textbook about translation from English into Russian. M., 1973.
5. Retsker Y.I. Theory of translation and translation practice. M., 1974.
6. Maclin A. Reference Guide to English: A Handbook of English as a Second Language. Washington, D.C., 1996. - 405 p.
7. Gordon E.M., Krylova I. P. Grammar of Present-Day English. Moscow, 1973. - 336 p.